

INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM THEORY AND ITS ROLE IN
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ANNOTATION.

The relationship between classical and quantum theory is central to the philosophy of physics, and any interpretation of quantum mechanics must clarify this relationship. Apart from gravity, quantum mechanics explains almost all known phenomena, from the structure of atoms, the laws of chemistry and condensed matter to the structure of the nucleus and the physics of elementary particles. It does all this with unprecedented precision. But almost 90 years after its discovery, there is general agreement that we still do not have a deep understanding of quantum mechanics, as we do with the measurement problem. The combination of ideas and methods does not completely solve the measurement problem, but the classical situation states that some states and quantum theory arise from the elimination of observables. Consequently, the classical world was created not by observation, but by its scarcity. Quantum theory is an extraordinarily successful theory of physics. But how does the mechanistic concept of nature underlying classical physics affect this theory? It is noteworthy that almost 90 years after the creation of quantum theory, there are still no clear answers to these questions. This article describes the nature of the obstacles that stand in the way of scientists and how quantum theory tries to overcome them by reconstructing mathematics from a few simple physical ideas.

Key words . Quantum theory, fundamentals of quantum theory, classical physics, quantum formalism

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Quantum theory is perhaps the most experimentally successful theory in the history of physics. In the ninety years since its creation, it has given us precise mathematical models that explain a wide range of physical phenomena, from the principles of chemical bonding and the nuclear reactions that ignite stars to exotic phenomena such as superconductivity and superfluidity. presented . In conclusion, for ninety years, quantum theory has been a faithful companion of physicists and has been responsible for providing constant new mathematical models of physical phenomena. Quantum theory also forms the

basis of modern technologies that support our lives. Quantum theory is required to design and model the transistor, which forms the basis of modern computing. The same is true of lasers and light-emitting diodes, which form the basis of optical communication networks (the backbone of the telecommunications industry) and optical data storage (such as CDs and DVDs).

Technologies such as advanced quantum computers and quantum encryption are also rapidly entering our lives. Due to the experimental successes of quantum theory, there is no doubt that the mathematical rules of quantum theory correctly reflect the basic properties of the physical world. Since their formulation ninety years ago, there have been very strong indications that these rules describe a physical reality that cannot be maintained from the perspective of reality that forms the basis of classical physics. However, the exact nature of the quantum formalism in understanding the material world remains unclear. To better understand the nature and importance of the problem, it is useful to start with a review of classical physics. Classical physics, as fundamental physics, is a clear understanding of the essence of reality as set forth in the pioneering works of seventeenth-century figures such as Descartes, Galileo, and Newton. The basic idea is that everything that exists in the phenomenal world (that is, the side of the world recorded by perceptual or instrumental extensions such as a microscope or a telescope) moves with a universal step in the stationary phase of matter. Mathematical time is fully consistent with deterministic laws of motion. In principle, this entity can be interrogated at will without disturbing its nature or motion, and through such interrogations the underlying laws of motion can be determined and thus a theoretical model of physical reality can be found. This theory makes it possible to predict the behavior of physical systems. When considered directly mathematically, this concept includes not only Newtonian mechanics, but also classical physical theories - mainly electromagnetism (which describes the phenomena of electricity and magnetism) - which form the mathematical basis of thermodynamics explains the classical mathematical framework and two classical systems. statistical mechanics (heat and temperature phenomena) built after Newton during the century. Thus, classical physics has a two-fold structure: (i) a strictly intelligible concept of reality that we can easily understand without mathematics (a mechanical representation of material reality) and (ii) a mathematical foundation. This dual structure has important consequences in classical physics. First, this dual structure gained flexibility in the development of classical physics. Second, this "world of time" view of the phenomenal world was easily

understood by people with no knowledge of mathematics. As a result, this view was not limited to the physics community, but spread to other fields (chemistry, biology, psychology, economics, and sociology) that successfully adapted mathematical methods developed by physicists. More broadly, this view spread beyond the sciences to fields such as philosophy and theology, and was instrumental in the radical changes that took place in the 300 years after Newton's publication of mechanics.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Although quantum physics, unlike classical physics, has a mathematical basis that can be used to model physical systems, it lacks a clear understanding of physical reality. To understand how this situation came about, it is useful to consider some historical approaches. Historical Development By the 1890s, classical physics was in a very advanced state. Newtonian mechanics explained both the motion of bodies on Earth and detailed astronomical observations of the orbits of planets, moons, and comets; Maxwell's electromagnetism provided a comprehensive understanding of electrical and magnetic phenomena (including a quantitative explanation of the phenomenon of light) and detailed thermodynamics, the phenomenon of heat, and the process of converting heat into useful mechanical motion. However, there were also some question marks: there were empirical facts that stubbornly resisted these theories. One of these facts was related to the frequencies of light emitted by heated objects (classical theories did not even qualitatively take into account experimental data). Provisional explanations for these facts (initiated by Max Planck) lead to the development of quantum theory, a completely new theoretical basis for physical theories that replaced the mathematical basis of classical physics.

Quantum theory clearly and in principle did not exist. On the contrary, the formation path was difficult and difficult to generalize. In essence, the construction of the quantum formula was guided by heuristic ideas (for example, the idea that each particle is associated with a "guiding wave") and ingenious mathematical assumptions about which aspects of the existing mathematical structures in classical physics were required. It is worth noting that the conceptual framework was not complete, and although it did not constitute a coherent picture of reality, it was somewhat sufficient to provide an empirically sound mathematical framework (courtesy of Heisenberg and Schrödinger). One of the remarkable features of the quantum formalism it is. This is in contrast to the situation in classical physics, when a measurement is made in a quantum system, the result of the measurement is not completely determined by the state

of the system, but rather by the probability of the result. the state of the system, although it is unclear what the actual outcome will be.

That is, the obtained measurement result does not describe the state of the system immediately before the measurement. Given the importance of this property, it is surprising that there is no real uncertainty in the formulation of the quantum formalism. Indeed, when Schrödinger, one of the founders of the theory, wrote his famous quantum mechanical equation for the electron, he believed that it could be interpreted as a new type of fully deterministic classical field equation. Later it became clear that such an interpretation was impossible and Schrödinger's equation should be interpreted from the point of view of probability. Therefore, during the emergence of quantum theory in 1925-6, if a well-defined and empirically adequate mathematical foundation was created, the physical origin and meaning were unclear. After the quantum formalism was established, many results appeared showing that the reality described by quantum phenomena violated the basic principles of classical mechanics. For example, as mentioned above, one of these classical principles is that, in principle, the physical state of a system can be measured without making any changes to it. The quantum formalism, on the other hand, implies that this is not the case; The measurement, as a rule, can provide only partial information about the state of the system and can cause the system to fail. In addition, as mentioned above, the mechanistic understanding assumes that all measurement results are determined by the state of the system, while quantum phenomena cannot be completely determined by the state of the system and have inherent uncertainty.

These effects seemed to contradict the basic rules of the mechanistic view of classical physics. Most of the founders of quantum theory, such as Bohr, Heisenberg, and Pauli, believed that the above-mentioned effects should be taken seriously and the classical mechanical view should be replaced by something completely new. In order to shed light on these non-classical features in quantum theory, some physicists have tried to interpret existing concepts or develop new concepts in which these features can be taken as specific instances and thus include non-classical features . . . For example, Bohr developed the concept of complementarity. According to this concept;

- In any experiment, the participation process of experimental instruments and observation cannot be explained by conventional concepts.

- During the experimental process, no clear line can be drawn between the observation and the observed; because the process of observation affects what is being observed.
- Concepts such as wave and particle are inevitably used to describe the atomic world, but different models must be used for different experimental situations. These different models and situations should be seen as "complementary" rather than "opposite" because they do not appear under the same experimental conditions. (For example, an electron is a particle in one experimental state and a wave in another.) From Bohr's point of view, the impossibility of quantum theory to make a measurement that gives complete information about a physical system is a feature of the general principle of complementarity. Similarly, Heisenberg and Pauli suggested that Aristotle's concepts of potentiality and reality may be useful in understanding the relationship between the state of a system and the results of measurements made on the system, and why there are inconsistencies in classical thinking. The ideas discovered and developed by Bohr, Heisenberg, Pauli, and others were important first steps in developing the non-realistic mechanical understanding that underpins quantum theory. However, after their efforts, the development of a non-mechanical understanding in the direction they envisioned was not pursued by the majority of the physics community. As a result, today, since the creation of quantum theory qson years later, physicists believe after successfully applying it to very large multi-physical systems. They have a well-defined mathematical system, which they have heard about, but have not built a solid foundation for. The lack of such a fundamental understanding affects the development of physics in various ways. First, if one wants to discover new quantum phenomena or use quantum physics for new technologies, given the intuitive nature of the predictions, one needs some guidance on what interesting and useful quantum phenomena can emerge from quantum theory. Ground reality has the capacity to provide such guidance; On the contrary, the lack of such understanding hinders the rate of discovery of new phenomena and the rate of use of quantum physics.

Second, when trying to apply quantum theory to new physical fields, it will be especially important to channel human intuition. understanding the truth. For example, an important problem in theoretical physics is the construction of a quantum theory of gravity, a theory that somehow combines the concepts of

quantum theory and general relativity, the two great foundations of modern physics. When undertaking such a project, it is important to know what assumptions about the physical world are implicit in the quantum formalism. For example, is formality directly related to the structure of spacetime? If so, what is the nature of this addiction? More broadly, how does quantum theory relate to fundamental concepts in classical physics such as matter, energy, momentum, and locality?

Because we currently have no understanding of reality that supports the quantum formalism, the properties of the physical world on which quantum theory is based are unknown. From a broader interdisciplinary perspective, the lack of understanding of the reality underlying quantum formalism means that the essence of quantum theory does not correspond to other fields of science, and more broadly, to other fields. As a result of these attempts, primary methods (mainly, in some sense reformulating the quantum formalism) have borne fruit. Examples of recent findings are that quantum theory has nonlocal and nonclassical properties; Each of them clearly shows that quantum physics is the opposite of the mechanical view. For example, in the case of localization, if a pair of quantum systems is allowed to interact and then separated by an arbitrarily large distance, the results of individual measurements for each of them will lead to a so-called "local latent variable model" is found to be incalculable according to for real.

In short, it is clear that there is actually some connection between physical systems that have interacted in the past and persisted regardless of their distance, and that there is an idea that doubts small but real connections between them. . If so, this connection is of a type never seen in classical physics: unlike the forces of gravity, electricity, or magnetism, coupling is unaffected by distance and is inherent to systems that have previously interacted. This definition radically changes the status of space and the basic element of mechanical representation : space is no longer an entity that mediates all interactions between material bodies; Instead, it exists as an ever-changing web of communication between unnatural spatial systems.

Although these methods provide important information, their main limitation is that they use quantum theory in a particular way. When classical physics is naturally mathematized, man clearly understands reality. However, the quantum formalism has many mathematical constructs that cannot be found in the mathematical framework underlying classical physics. For example, states of systems are represented by complex vectors in complex vector space, and

temporal evolution of states is represented by unitary transformations of these vectors. Perhaps there are physical reasons for this condition, but what are those reasons? The aforementioned attempts to solve quantum theory cannot answer this question. In the last forty years, it has been realized that it is necessary to try to determine the relevance of physical ideas in the quantum formalism. That is, rather than accepting the theory in a certain way, it is necessary to work on the formulation of simple physical principles from which the quantum formalism can be derived. Restructuring the quantum formalism in this way transfers the physical content of the quantum formalism into a set of concrete expressions expressed in natural (everyday) language; Thus, the entire content of the quantum formalism becomes available for the necessary conceptual analysis. As a result, quantum theory continues to be reconstructed in detail based on different starting points. However, until now there is of work never one abstract mathematician assumptions without entering quantum theory standard in the form could not get

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Each sequence of measurement results obtained in a given experiment is represented by a pair of real numbers, and the probability of performing the function of both components of this sequence is not continuous. Using the basic conditions of symmetry and consistency, and without assuming that these pairs of real numbers have no other algebraic structure, these pairs have been found to be manipulated according to complex arithmetic rules. Furthermore, these complex numbers were found to obey Feynman's rules of summation, which, when combined with the square of the moduli, gave the probability of a sequence of outcomes. The dual assumption at the heart of the approach states that a measurement of a physical system can only provide information about half of the system's degrees of freedom.

This is a formalization of Bohr's principle of complementarity. In classical mechanics, it is assumed that a particle can be given exact values of position and velocity at the same time. However, an assumption of quantum theory is that it is possible to specify either the exact value of the position or the properties of the velocity at the same time, but not both. To understand this quantum limitation in the fundamental classical concept, Bohr developed the "Principle of Complementarity". According to this principle, any description of a physical phenomenon is closely related to a certain empirical arrangement, such an arrangement to the exclusion of other aspects of the phenomenon that are equally necessary for a complete description of the phenomenon in classical

thought. used for . Inspired in part by the dialectical aspect of Kierkegaard's philosophical thought, this principle is a special case of a general philosophical principle. Discovering the generality of the principle, Bohr and others showed similar phenomena in the mental and organic spheres. Pauli, for example, developed an analogy between physical complementarity and the relationship between the unconscious and conscious aspects of mental experience.

And modern psychology reveals the largely objective reality of the unconscious psyche; each of them gives rise to consciousness, that is, to observation, to interaction with unconscious content that cannot be controlled in principle; This situation limits the objective character of unconscious reality and separates reality with a certain subjectivity. Two main assumptions are made within the article. First, there is the operational assumption of uncertainty, meaning that probability is inherent in measurements. Second, complementarity implies that only half of the degrees of freedom required for the theoretical description of the system can be achieved in a given experiment. Both of these assumptions are the degrees of freedom of a system with uncertainty (the measurement result is determined by the state of the system) and fundamental principles (that is, in principle, there is only one criterion that can be reached) from the mechanical point of view of classical physics. all). If ambiguity and complementarity are accepted as givens, what understanding of nature is offered? The reconstruction of quantum theory, as described above, is an important step towards a new "Concept of Nature", because it focuses our attention on only a small number of non-classical properties, but it is still a step. An important part of understanding is providing a unified understanding of the particular assumptions underlying the reconstruction. The ambiguity and overlap in the reconstruction described above is suggested for fundamentally different reasons. Therefore, in this case, it is necessary to explain why Nature has the properties of ambiguity and complementarity, and not just one or the other.

Summary

How to deal with such an idea philosophically? In the case of complementarity, why is it that the measurement can reach, say, half of the state degrees of freedom of the system and not the rest?

Today, all of these questions remain unanswered, and some are the focus of ongoing research. More broadly, it is still an open question whether a new understanding of nature is really necessary to understand uncertainty and complementarity, or whether they are supported by a classical mechanistic understanding of reality. The idea expressed in the article is that the most

effective way forwarded long ago by Bohr and Pauli is to accept complementarity and uncertainty as the main features of reality and understand their nature by improving our understanding. It should be clear that there is deep psychological resistance to such ideas among physicists. However, various physicists such as Bohm and Wheeler tried to develop new concepts of reality based on some non-classical features of quantum theory.

The view of demonstrable truth is essentially participatory truth: scientists have unlimited freedom to choose what questions Nature chooses from among their measurements (the illogicality of this choice is guaranteed by complementarity), and the answer is partially determined by the experimental variables. control.. This answer puts a part of reality in the position of defining it precisely at the expense of another feature that is transformed into another state. Thus, the temporal trajectory of reality is closely related to the choices made. In this understanding, the existing state is not a fully defined state, but rather one where there is a spectrum between complete definition and completeness. A surprising feature of the above reconstruction is that it does not mention the location or its features. This appears to be a sharp critique of Kurodinger and Heisenberg's approach to quantum formalism, and is considered to be at the beginning of classical spatial thought.

That is, the above reconstruction strongly supports the idea that the quantum formalism does not depend on space and its properties; that is, space is not spatially spatial. This basically shows that the classical mechanistic view that what exists in space is matter is wrong and that what exists is independent of space. This view was already advanced by Bell; The above reconstruction supports this idea more clearly. This view is particularly important for the quantum gravity program, suggesting that a theory should be sought in which spacetime rather than location first emerges.

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